

The bark is credited with diuretic, antipyretic and alexertic properties. The fruit is also useful as diuretic and the fruit-peel as hypnotic agent¹. Lapachol has been reported as an anti-tumour compound² and has also been recently used as an one-colour acid-base indicator³. Hentriacontanol^{4,5} is reported to be insecticide, fungicide and is also physiologically active. Literature reveals that no work, however, has been reported on any part of *T. pentaphylla* though studies on relation between heartwood fibre and its pulp sheet properties have been reported by Tamolang *et al*⁶.

The present note deals with the examination of the leaves and the stem heartwood of this tree. Both, leaves and stem heartwood were exhaustively extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°) and chromatographed over silica gel separately. Elution of the columns with the solvents of increasing polarity afforded the following compounds.

Leaves :

1. *Hentriacontanol-1* : Petroleum ether eluate, m.p. 84°, acetate (Ac₂O/pyridine), m. p. 69° and comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with an authentic specimen* confirmed its identity as hentriacontanol.

2. *Hentriacontane* : Petroleum ether-benzene (3 : 1) eluate, m.p. 64°, M⁺(436) confirmed its identity as hentriacontane.

3. *Dehydrotectol* : Petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) eluate, m.p. 193-94°, its conversion into tectol and comparison (m. m. p., co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic specimen confirmed its identity as dehydrotectol.

4. *Lapachol* : Petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 3) eluate, m.p. 139-40°, positive towards colour test for quinonoid compounds having chelated hydroxy group⁷. Its conversion into β -lapachone and comparison (m. m. p., co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic sample confirmed its identity as lapachol.

5. β -*Sitosterol* : Benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) eluate, m.p. 136-37°, positive to Liebermann-Burchard test⁸, acetate m.p. 126°, benzoate m.p. 143-43° and comparison (m. m. p., co-tlc and co-ir) with an authentic specimen confirmed its identity.

Stem Heartwood :

1. *Nonacosane* : Petroleum ether eluate, m.p. 62°, M⁺(408), was identified as nonacosane.

2. *Dehydro-tectol* : Petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 3) eluate, m.p. 193-94°, confirmed by direct comparison (m. m. p., co-tlc and co-ir) with an authentic specimen.

3. *Lapachol* : Petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) eluate, m.p. 139-40°, identical (m. m. p., co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic sample of lapachol.

* Some obtained from Prof. K. C. Joshi of the University of Rajasthan, Jaipur and some isolated by the authors themselves (*Die Pharmazie*, 1980, 35, 122).

4. β -*Sitosterol* : Benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) eluate, m.p. 136-37°, identical (m. m. p., co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic sample of β -sitosterol.

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Chemical Constituents of *Atalantia monophylla* (Correa)

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ATALANTIA monophylla Correa (Fam. Rutaceae), a medicinal plant¹ collected from Orissa, has been shown to contain acridone alkaloids², limonoids³⁻⁴ and several other compounds⁵. Further investigation of the petroleum ether extract of the leaves and benzene extract of the heartwood led to the isolation of *n*-butyl palmitate and β -sitosterol (leaves) and palmitic, stearic and arachidic acids (heartwood).

Finely ground dried leaves of *Atalantia monophylla* (6.2 Kg) were extracted with cold petroleum ether (60-80°) for 25 days. The concentrated extract (58 g) was chromatographed over silica gel to furnish an ester fraction, which on rechromatography gave *n*-butyl palmitate (I) C₂₀H₄₀O₂ (1.18 g) as a yellowish liquid; b.p. 165-170°/10 mm; ir: $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{NaCl}}$ 1375 cm⁻¹ (>C=O, ester); MS: m/e 312 (M⁺).

Alkaline hydrolysis of I gave palmitic acid identified by direct comparison with an authentic sample. Conversion of palmitic acid into its *n*-butyl ester gave a compound which had the same retention time as I on glc.

The identity of β -sitosterol m.p. 137-39°, was established by direct comparison with an authentic sample.

The cold benzene extract of the powdered heartwood of *Atalantia monophylla* on column chromatography over silica gel afforded an acid fraction (5%). The glc analysis of its methyl ester showed three major peaks corresponding to palmitic, stearic and arachidic methyl esters in the ratio 8 : 4 : 1, as well as minute quantities of C_{19} acids. The mass spectra of the acid mixture showed three M^+ peaks at m/e 256 (palmitic), 284 (stearic) and 312 (arachidic) and fragmentation peaks at regular interval of 14 mass units.

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Constituents of *Eupatorium riparium* Regel

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IN course of our studies on the chemical constituents of some Indian medicinal plants we investigated on the whole plant of *E. riparium* which has led to the isolation of taraxasteryl palmitate (I), taraxasteryl acetate (II), *epi*-friedelinol (III) and stigmasterol. Earlier work on the plant *E. riparium* Regel, however, resulted in the isolation of taraxasteryl palmitate, taraxasterol and stigmasterol¹ and chromones^{2,3}. This is thus the first report of the isolation of taraxasteryl acetate (II) and *epi*-friedelinol (III) from *E. riparium*.

Air-dried milled whole plant of *E. riparium* (3 kg) collected from the sub-Himalayan range in the month of April, 1976 was percolated with light petrol at room temperature for 10 days. The marc was again extracted exhaustively with chloroform at room temperature by percolation. Both extracts were concentrated separately by distilling off the solvent.

Taraxasteryl palmitate (I), *epi*-friedelinol (III) and stigmasterol were isolated from the petrol

extract. Taraxasteryl palmitate¹(I), $C_{46}H_{80}O_2$ (M^+ 664.6171), m.p. 95°, $[\alpha]_D +70^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$, c 0.17) was isolated as colourless needles (3 g, 0.1%) (petrol-acetone) from the petrol eluates during the chromatographic separation of the petrol extract over silica gel. It showed positive TNM colouration and exhibited ir (KBr) bands at 1722 (C=O), 1630 (C=C) and 860 cm^{-1} (C=CH₂); ¹H nmr signals ($CDCl_3$) at δ 4.60 (2H, *m*, C=CH₂), 4.45 (1H, *m*, >CH-O-CO-), 2.26 (2H, *t*, $J=6$ Hz, -CH₂COO-) and ¹³C nmr signals ($CDCl_3$) at δ 173.4 (CO), 154.3 (C-20), 107.1 (C-30), 80.5 (C-3), 55.4 (C-5), 50.3 (C-9), 48.6 (C-18), 42.0 (C-14), 40.9 (C-8), 39.2 (C-22 or C-16), 39.1 (C-16 or C-22), 38.8 (C-13), 38.4 (C-19 and C-1), 37.7 (C-4), 37.0 (C-10), 34.7 (C-2'), 34.4 (C-17), 33.9 (C-7), 31.9 (C-14'), 29.6 (C-4' to C-13'), 27.9 (C-23), 26.6 (C-15), 26.1 (C-28), 25.6 (C-12 and C-21), 25.1 (C-3'), 23.7 (C-2), 22.6 (C-15'), 21.4 (C-11), 19.4 (C-29), 18.1 (C-6 and C-16'), 16.5 (C-24), 16.2 (C-26), 15.9 (C-25) and 14.7 (C-27).

I on saponification with 5% KOH afforded taraxasterol (IV), $C_{30}H_{50}O$ (M^+ 426), m.p. 218°, $[\alpha]_D +55^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$, c 0.17). It gave Lieberman Burchard colouration reaction for triterpenes and showed ν_{max} (KBr) at 3400 (OH), 1633, 870 cm^{-1} ; ¹H nmr signals ($CDCl_3$) at δ 4.62 (2H, *d*, $J=2.2$ Hz, C=CH₂), 3.22 (1H, *m*, CHOH), 1.05, 1.01, 0.97, 0.94, 0.93, 0.85 and 0.76 (21H, seven singlets, methyl protons) and ¹³C nmr signals ($CDCl_3$) at δ 154.4 (C-20), 107.0 (C-30), 78.9 (C-3), 55.3 (C-5), 50.4 (C-9), 48.5 (C-18), 41.9 (C-14), 40.8 (C-8), 39.2 (C-22 or C-16), 39.1 (C-16 or C-22), 38.7 (C-1 and C-13), 38.2 (C-19), 37.0 (C-10), 34.4 (C-17), 34.0 (C-7), 27.9 (C-23), 27.3 (C-2), 26.6 (C-15), 26.1 (C-28), 25.5 (C-12 or C-21), 25.4 (C-21 or C-12), 21.3 (C-11), 19.3 (C-29), 18.2 (C-6), 16.1 (C-26), 15.8 (C-25), 15.2 (C-24) and 14.6 (C-27). IV was identical with an authentic sample of taraxasterol (m. m. p., ir and co-tlc).

IV on acetylation formed taraxasteryl acetate (II), $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$ (M^+ 468), m.p. 243°, $[\alpha]_D +99^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$, c 0.16) which exhibited ν_{max} (KBr) at 1732, 1245 cm^{-1} ; ¹H nmr signals ($CDCl_3$) at δ 4.61 (2H, *d*, $J=2.2$ Hz, C=CH₂), 4.46 (1H, *m*, CHOAc), 1.07, 1.02, 0.98, 0.93, 0.88, 0.85 and 0.85 (21H, seven singlets, methyl protons) and ¹³C nmr chemical shifts ($CDCl_3$) at δ 170.8 (C=O), 154.4 (C-20), 107.0 (C-30), 80.8 (C-3), 55.4 (C-5), 50.3 (C-9), 48.6 (C-18), 41.9 (C-14), 40.8 (C-8), 39.3 (C-22 or C-16), 39.1 (C-16 or C-22), 38.8 (C-13), 38.4 (C-1), 38.3 (C-19), 37.7 (C-4), 37.0 (C-10), 34.4 (C-17), 33.9 (C-7), 27.8 (C-23), 26.6 (C-15), 26.1 (C-28), 25.5 (C-12 or C-21), 25.4 (C-21 or C-12), 23.6 (C-2), 21.4 (C-11), 21.1 (COCH₃), 19.4 (C-29), 18.1 (C-6), 16.4 (C-24), 16.2 (C-26), 15.8 (C-25) and 14.6 (C-27). The above data and high resolution mass spectrum of I were in conformity with its assigned structure. The assignment of the various chemical shifts of I, II and IV were made by comparison with the resonances for